

IRRIGATION WATER SCHEDULING OF THE DRIP SYSTEM FOR AUTOMATION AND CONSERVATION IN AGRICULTURAL CULTIVATIONAL FARMS

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etc.*

Abstract: *This work, conducted in Ozoro, Nigeria, encompassed the water schedule of the drip irrigation system for automation and conservation in agricultural cultivation farms. Corn was used in four growth stage categorization. The root zone features like the rooting depth and the soil type were used in determining the net irrigation, while other parameters like the irrigation efficiency, gross irrigation depth, evaporation, water schedule, number of irrigations, and irrigation interval were also obtained. It was found that the root zone had a shallow rooting depth of 30 cm to 60 cm, with soil types of sandy and loamy. The corn number of cultivation in days was 143 days. Net irrigation was 15 mm and 20 mm for sandy and loamy respectively. Irrigation efficiency was 90 %. Gross irrigation depth was 17 mm and 22 mm, respectively. Evaporation was 8 mm. Water scheduling was 2 and 3 days, respectively. The number of irrigation schedules was 4 and 4.4 irrigations. And, schedule irrigation interval was 20 and 18 days, respectively. Observationally, the combination of scheduling and the drip techniques in the irrigation system established a higher level of automation goals attainable in the farm land, and inturn provided more conservation than could have been achieved individually. These data are vital for decision making in agricultural farms, especially in the deployment of irrigation automation prior to automatic water timers, maintaining notable efficient irrigation, and conservation of natural resources like soil and water, and artificial resources like human labour and machines in cultivational farms.*

***Okolotu G.I., Eje B.E., Akwenuke O.M., and Okeke C.G.**

I.

INTRODUCTION

Drylands comprise of more than 40% of the earth's land area, also home to approximately 2.5 billion people, and account for about 50% of livestock and 45% of global food production (Singh and Chudasama, 2021; Xing and Wang, 2024), entailing its vitality. Most of these lands require irrigation for cultivational maximization. Large - scale agriculture was introduced in the 1940s (NGS, 2024), and has made landmark impact with more prospects for the future. The increase in production scale compliments the water consumption rate, which irrigation strategies potentially conserve.

Irrigation is the application of water from place of abundance to where it is required. Irrigation has been a key aspect of agriculture for over 5,000 years (Wikipedia, 2024), with surface irrigation method otherwise gravity irrigation, as the oldest form of irrigation. In Africa, the oldest irrigated agriculture (with archaeological evidence) was practiced in Egypt about 5000 years BC, possessing large flat basins built for floods diversion used in growing winter crops along the Nile riverbanks (Angelak *et al.*, 2020). Water management in agricultural sector is very vital and requires immediate attention (Chaudhary &, Srivastava, 2021). Precipitation is a major source of natural water (Okolotu *et al.*, 2023; Okolotu *et al.* 2024). According to Singh and Chudasama, (2021), "volatility in precipitation significantly affects the availability of water resources essential for

the sustainability of agriculture and ecosystems". Hence, precipitation needs supplementation. Agriculture has been regarded as a significant water user sector as it abstracts 70% of the global freshwater resources for the irrigation of 25% of the global croplands (Bwambale *et al.*, 2022). Sufficient availability of water in the root zone is crucial throughout the growing season of a crop (Adu *et al.*, 2018), for moisture maintenance in soils. Advancing from traditional ponding methods to water saving production techniques tackles the inability to provide adequate water that meet evaporative demands, weed and pest infestations, labor demand increase, *etc.* Advancement of this sort remain complemented to modern irrigation strategies. Such irrigation strategies point towards the frequencing and how much water is best irrigatably applicable. How much an irrigation water is applicable based on the frequency with respect to required crop water is categorizable into full irrigation and deficit irrigation. Adu *et al.*, (2018), and Xi *et al.*, (2021) emphasized that "we can differentiate between full irrigation, *i.e.*, frequent irrigation events replacing the water demanded by the crop, and deficit irrigation, *i.e.*, supplying less water than that demanded by the crop, and usually with low irrigation frequencies". Advanced irrigation technologies, such as sprinkler systems, drip irrigation, and micro - irrigation, minimize water loss from evaporation, thereby ensuring a

***Okolotu G.I., Eje B.E., Akwenuke O.M., and Okeke C.G.**

more efficient utilization of water resources (Qi *et al.*, 2024; Xing and Wang, 2024).

Water scheduling refers to appropriation in timing and quantity of water usage. Irrigation water scheduling is the decision of when and how much, water is applied to the field and thus, has a direct effect on water use efficiency (Bwambale *et al.*, 2022). Xi *et al.*, (2021), explained that "Irrigation scheduling consists of determining both the timing of irrigation in relation of when to apply an irrigation event, and the amount of water to be supplied with each irrigation event". Accurate irrigation is critical to agricultural output and management (Hossain *et al.*, 2024), attainable prior advance techniques of irrigation scheduling. Without advanced irrigation management, over - or under - irrigation may occur, leading to several negative environmental and economic impacts (Datta *et al.*, 2018), which due schedule may prevent. The crop quality and yield are significantly dependent on the amount of water and timing (Umutoni and Samadi, 2024). In the case of over - irrigation, growers can lose money due to higher energy costs of pumping additional water without an economic increase in production. In addition, Datta *et al.*, (2018), explained that, "if the irrigation pumps are run more often, the wear and tear will decrease the overall lifespan". Under irrigation cause the full negativity as lack of irrigation water leading to drought and death of crops. Advantages of irrigation water scheduling are; (1), minimization of crop water stress. (2), minimization of irrigation water and labour cost.

(3), minimization of surface runoff (erosion) and deep percolation (leaching). (4), reduction of fertilizer application cost and wastage. (5), maximization of crop quality and yields for optimum net returns. (6), minimization of water - logging problems. Generally, the use of model based crop water need assessment are categorized into; Process based models, deterministic methods, and machine learning methods. Umutoni, and Samadi, (2024), explained that, process - based models usually determine crop water requirement by simulating biophysical processes leading to plants' growth in the soil - plant - atmosphere system using mathematical formulations of those processes, deterministic methods calculate irrigation water demand based on crop evapotranspiration approaches, and, machine learning models (data-driven) estimate irrigation needs by learning the hidden function that relates input weather and soil data to crop water demands.

Irrigation automation refers to the process of converting the controlling of an irrigation device or system components to a more automatic system. Conservation of human power otherwise manual labour for the utmost desirable farming functions basically prompted the need of irrigation automation. Other need also abound depending on posing requirements capable of influencing cultivational decisions. Automation of irrigation has the potential to resolve some of these issues (Champness *et al.*, 2023). It has been used for water and fertilizer delivery to farmlands. This

***Okolotu G.I., Eje B.E., Akwenuke O.M., and Okeke C.G.**

irrigation innovational adversary in trend is effectively maximizable prior sensed data. Automation necessitates and maximizes the use of machines in agriculture. This influences the application of computerized components in irrigation system for automatic water delivery. With the advances in machine - to - machine (M2M) platforms that are a part of internet of a thing (IoT), it has become possible for different devices to communicate with each other without human (Sidhu *et al.*, 2021), while maintaining same or more output. Fundamentally, according to Champness *et al.*, (2023), the minimum components of an automated irrigation system to reduce or replace the work previously done by humans requires a water outlet controller, sensors to measure desired parameters (*e.g.*, water height, soil moisture, temperature, *etc*), a supervisory system to process, or and interpret sensed data and take actions based on such inputs, a user interface and a communication network to enable connectivity between devices and the supervisory system. Irrigation automation major system components include: Sensor (for gathering data on soil moisture and climatic conditions, enables precise watering, as well as prevent under or over - irrigation), management software (processes sensor data and makes decisions, as well as streamlines irrigation schedules), nozzle (for delivering and distributing water to plants), internet of things (for connecting devices and sensors for communication, as well as facilitates remote control and system monitoring).

Water conservation refers to the wise utilization of natural resources attributed to water with respect of protection, preservation, guarding, *etc.*, for proper management. It is a "do more with less" approach without compromising performance. Water is a finite resource, and its supply on earth today is the same as what was here at the beginning of the planet (WSDE, 2024). This calls for proper conservancies, as not all earth supplied water is readily available to human use. According to Udom *et al.*, (2023), globally 99.7 percent water is in the oceans, icecaps, soils, and atmosphere. The remaining 0.3 % contribute to other human usages. The ocean covers 97% of the earth hydrosphere, and only 3% of which is fresh water, is suitable for living beings, including humans (Rao *et al.*, 2024). Less than this 3% freshwater on earth have been estimated to be available for human use. RHV, (2024), noted that "Only 1% of the entire water supply on earth is available for human use with the rest being salty or locked in ice caps and glaciers, and this 1% keeps all of the world's agricultural, community and personal household, manufacturing, and sanitation purposes operating". Water availability affect the supply which is influencible by population growth, climate change, and expansion of industry and agriculture (GBC, 2024), and, inevitably demanding conservation. "According to the United Nations, over 40% of the global population currently experiences water shortages, and this figure is expected to grow in the coming years" (Button, 2023). Water

***Okolotu G.I., Eje B.E., Akwenuke O.M., and Okeke C.G.**

conservation focuses on improving the effectiveness of water use through various means, such as choosing to change behavior (AWWA, 2025). Such modifiable choices for conservatory in agricultural water use require advances in cultivational techniques. With respect to this study, include scheduling and Irrigation.

Drip irrigation is the application of irrigation water with flow features of tiny drops, in a one after the other sequence. Drip irrigation is the slow, even application of low pressure water to soil and plants using plastic tubing placed directly at the plants root zone (Shock, 2024), to attain a desirable soil moisture. Drip irrigation systems provide water as well as nutrients, to the crop root zone, where it becomes most effectively utilized (Sidhu *et al.*, 2021), preventing unnecessary out loss of water from cultivated to uncultivated field. Guo and Li, (2024), explained that "drip water infiltrates the soil of the crop root zone through emitters, creating a moist area with a high soil water content (SWC) within a 0–20 cm range on either side of the drip line". The plants easily assess the soil water through capillary uptake by

their roots connection in the soil. Taghvaeian, (2017), emphasized that the capability of delivering water precisely at the plant root spot where nearly all of the water can be used for plant growth, differentiate the drip irrigation from sprinklers which irrigate the entire field surface. Qi *et al.*, (2024), narrated that "drip irrigation offers many significant advantages over surface irrigation, including potential water - saving, higher fertilizer efficiency, improved crop yield quality and homogeneity, adaptability to various field shapes, sizes, and slopes, and reduced labor costs". Drip system can significantly enhance the soil water content in the shallow (0–40 cm) and middle layers (40–60 cm) of farmland (Guo and Li, 2024). The drip irrigation systems are customizably suitable for different soil types, crops, and farm landscapes, making them versatile and sustainable water conservation solution for agriculture, capable of aiding farmers conserve water by minimizing weed growth as well as, reducing disease incidence, as the plant foliage remain dry. A typical exemplary of the drip installation layout is presented in figure one (1) below;

***Okolotu G.I., Eje B.E., Akwenuke O.M., and Okeke C.G.**

Figure 1: Drip system set up for irrigation (by site photography at study area)

Section i depicts a water harnessing from groundwater source, ii denotes a portable artificial reservoir for storage, III is a mark out empty land, IV is a cultivated land with irrigation drip pipe channeling for water application. The reservoir tank was associably portable and attributively possessing advantages and disadvantages. The size offers low cost of purchase and components installation, replaceability, farm space

manageability, *etc.* On the other hand, it is easily moveable, and thus vulnerable to theft susceptibility.

II. MATERIALS

The study area is a section of the demonstration farm at Delta state university of science and technology, Ozoro in Nigeria. Ozoro is situated in southern region of delta state, as well as southern (west) part of nigeria, in west africa. The location of the study area is presented in figure two (2) below;

***Okolotu G.I., Eje B.E., Akwenuke O.M., and Okeke C.G.**

Figure 2: Map location of the study area in Ozoro, Nigeria (Okolotu *et al.*, 2025)

Other materials used include: site camera, metal soil auger, neutron probe, *etc.*

III. METHODS

Upon necessary literatures, the irrigation water schedule of installed drip system at the study location was deduced following relevant procedures.

Net irrigation was obtained prior root zone measurements within the irrigated soil depth with respect to its soil type (texture) readings. Corn rooting depth were thus measured and classified as a shallow rooting crop, *i.e.*, between 30 to 60 cm. The soil type was also evaluated and found to be sandy and loamy which were traceable to 15 mm and 20 mm respectively. This can be traceably seen in table one (1) below;

Table 1: Soil type with different rooting depth of crops for net irrigation rating

S/N	Soil Type	Shallow Rooting Crops Of 30 to 60 cm	Medium Rooting Crops Of 50 to 100 cm	Deep Rooting Crops Of 90 to 150 cm
1	Sandy	15	30	40
2	Loamy	20	40	60

Irrigation efficiency was obtained based on the assessment of the system water conservation capacity (ability to deliver water that infiltrate the soil, with emphasis on wastage minimization). It ratios the infiltrated and stored water in root zone to the applied water depth (Scherer and Steele, 2024). System application efficiency therefore equals (amount of water that infiltrated into the soil otherwise net ÷ amount of water applied to the soil otherwise gross) × 100. This was assessed validatively in accordance of drip method, giving 90 % to 98 % water saving capacity. On an average, 7.2 mm infiltrated water from seted

8 mm application where 0.8 mm was lost to the atmosphere before plant use. Thus, giving;

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Drip efficiency, \%} &= (7.2 \div 8) \times 100 \\ &= 0.9 \times 100 \\ &= 90 \% \text{ efficient.} \end{aligned}$$

Gross irrigation depth for the two soil types of the area were obtained with respect to the net irrigation and efficiency in line with Price, (2019), as below;

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Gross irrigation depth (sandy soil), } d &= (100 \times \\ \text{Net irrigation)} \div \text{Irrigation efficiency} \\ \text{Thus, } d &= (100 \times 15) \div 90 \\ &= 1500 \div 90 \\ &= 17 \text{ mm} \end{aligned}$$

***Okolotu G.I., Eje B.E., Akwenuke O.M., and Okeke C.G.**

Gross irrigation depth (loamy soil), $d = (100 \times \text{Net irrigation}) \div \text{Irrigation efficiency}$

Thus, $d = (100 \times 20) \div 90$

$= 2000 \div 90$

$= 22 \text{ mm}$

Water scheduling was obtained based on irrigation water depth and cumulative pan evaporation, in line with FAO, (1989), as presented below;

$S = \text{IWD} \div \text{CPE}$

Where: IWD is the gross irrigation depth. CPE is the evaporation cumulated from pan measurement.

The electronic neutron probe was used in obtaining CPE. Validatively, the area classification as semiarid region or sub - humid climate with high temperature of above 25°C , on the average was 38°C . Thus, evaporation was obtained as 8 mm/day. This was classified as high ET, with respect to ET ratings of low (4 to 5 mm/day), medium (6 to 7 mm/day), and, high (8 to 9 mm/day).

Therefore, irrigation water scheduling (sandy soil), $S = 17 \div 8$

$= 2.13$

Thus, approximately 2 days.

Also, irrigation water scheduling (loamy soil), $S = 22 \div 8$

$= 2.75$

$= 2.75$

Thus, approximately 3 days.

IV. RESULTS

The obtained results are presented in tables two (2) and three (3) and figures three (3) to five (5) below;

Table 2: Obtained results for sandy soil

Therefore the field was schedulable to be irrigated for sandy soil every 2 days interval with 17 mm of irrigation water with respect to depth. And, for loamy soil every 3 days interval with 22 mm of irrigation water with respect to depth.

These processes were replicated for the four cultivational stages of the plant. Thus, total irrigation water required (WR) for sandy soil was 17 mm + 17 mm + 17 mm + 17 mm, yielding 68 mm/day of WR. While, total irrigation water required (WR) for loamy soil was 22 mm + 22mm + 22 mm + 22mm, yielding 88 mm/day of WR.

Number of irrigation, $\text{NI} = \text{WR} \div d$

For sandy soil, number of irrigation, $\text{NI} = 68 \text{ mm/day} \div 17 \text{ mm}$

$= 4 \text{ irrigations required.}$

For loamy soil, number of irrigation, $\text{NI} = 88 \text{ mm/day} \div 20 \text{ mm}$

$= 4.4 \text{ irrigations required.}$

Also, irrigation interval, $I = \text{Duration of cultivation} \div \text{Number of irrigations}$

In roll one (1) of tables two (2) and three (3), irrigation intervals were obtained as below;

For sandy soil, $I = 80 \text{ days} \div 4$

$= 20 \text{ days}$

For loamy soil, $I = 80 \text{ days} \div 4.4$

$= 18 \text{ days}$

S/N	Cultivation Stage	Corn Cultivation No. Of Days	Net Irrigation (mm)	Irrigation Efficiency (%)	Gross Irrigation Depth, d (mm)	Evaporation, CPE (mm/day)	Irrigation Scheduling, S (days)	Number Of Irrigation, NI	Irrigation Schedule Interval, I (days)
1	Planting - flowering	80	15	90	17	8	2	4	20
2	Flowering - fruiting	16	15	90	17	8	2	4	4
3	Fruiting - ripening	29	15	90	17	8	2	4	7
4	Ripening - harvest	18	15	90	17	8	2	4	5
Sum	4	143	60	360	68	32	8	16	36
Av.	-	36	15	90	17	8	2	4	9

The loamy soil results are presented in table three (3) below;

Table 3: Obtained results for loamy soil

S/N	Cultivation Stage	Corn Cultivation No. Of Days	Net Irrigation (mm)	Irrigation Efficiency (%)	Gross Irrigation Depth, d (mm)	Evaporation, CPE (mm/day)	Irrigation Scheduling, S (days)	Number Of Irrigation, NI	Irrigation Schedule Interval, I (days)
1	Planting - flowering	80	20	90	22	8	3	4.4	18
2	Flowering - fruiting	16	20	90	22	8	3	4.4	4
3	Fruiting - ripening	29	20	90	22	8	3	4.4	7
4	Ripening - harvest	18	20	90	22	8	3	4.4	4
Sum	4	143	80	360	88	32	12	17.6	33
Av.	-	36	20	90	22	8	3	4.4	8

The trend in schedule interval with respect to cultivation days at different growth stages for sandy and loamy soils are presented in figure three (3) below;

***Okolotu G.I., Eje B.E., Akwenuke O.M., and Okeke C.G.**

Figure 3: Trend in schedule interval with respect to cultivation days at different growth stages for sandy and loamy

Irrigation schedule, number of irrigation, and schedule interval for (I) sandy and (II) loamy soils are presented in figure four (4) below;

Figure 4: Irrigation schedule, number of irrigation, and schedule interval for (I) sandy and (II) loamy

Total outcome of irrigation parameters for (I) sandy and (II) loamy are presented in figure five (5) below;

Figure 5: Total

outcome of irrigation parameters for (I) sandy and (II) loamy

V. DISCUSSION

In the first growth stage, the intervals (20 and 18 days respectively) were long. This was considerate since the plants were yet to be more water demanding. Such was in accordance with Plumlee *et al.*, (2023) which reported that "Prior to germination, the corn seed absorbs water equal to approximately 50% of its weight". This may be associable to the root features with respect to size (short roots absorbs less while long roots absorbs more). Also, upon developing features (more stems or branches, seeds or fruits, *etc*) that warrant more water uptake, the interval were shortened to meet the crop water needs. Limitations of these results abound for sandy and loamy soils. Thus, such schedule data are attributive to Ozoro soils, and regions with features associated to the area. These include most places in Delta State regions, sandy and loamy soil regions of Nigeria and west Africa other than deserts, and, global regions with similar climatic and soil properties. Clayey was exclusive in this work because of the area unnoticeable possession.

The drip irrigation just like the sprinkler irrigation, and, center pivot irrigation (they apply water under pressure through pipe or tubing to the crops), are more water - use efficient than the gravity systems (which move water across the field by means of on - field gravity, though they allow water lost to runoff and evaporation *e.g.*, furrows, and basins irrigation). This was in concordance with, Guo and Li, (2024), which literally reported that drip irrigation save 20~50% water compared with flood irrigation techniques. The 90% drip efficiency obtained in this work invariably portray that such gravity technique of flood type can not be more than 70% efficient and can be as low as 40%. The drip system offered upto 90 % efficiency independently. This remarkable output makes the drip system a top class efficient field irrigation method, and, its combinative input with schedule rendered higher efficient irrigation. This combination establishes higher level of automation goals in the farm land. In turn provide more conservation of soil resources, water resources, human labour resources, and, even farm

***Okolotu G.I., Eje B.E., Akwenuke O.M., and Okeke C.G.**

machine resources. With respect to soil resources conservation, the drip system provides water specifically to only the soil areas within the root zones of plants, and, hence, discourages nutrient wastage outside the expected zone (weeds die on lack of soil water nutrient, channellable to desirable crops), and with scheduling, the system prevent erosion of soil due to over irrigation, maintain healthy soil aeration prior over and under irrigation, *etc*. In regard of conserving water resources, the drip system provides water in flow of tiny drops thereby preventing unwanted water outpours and with schedule, excessive tiny drops wastage after attaining peak irrigation are saved for the next scheduled interval prior water application, thereby preventing loss of water resources that could have occurred after peak supply. In terms of conservation of human labour resources, drip system require human input intentionally in turning on and off, prior system switch and controls, with schedule, such services become minimal, enabling the labour output vacuum to be filled with other important task. In respect to the conservation of machine resources, drip system are designably installed with machine

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components like reservoir engine pumps for water abstraction, plumbed equipment for water distribution, and drippers for water application, and with scheduling, the system functionality becomes periodical prior desired interval, thereby prolonging the wear and tear of the machine units of the system.

VI. CONCLUSION

The data obtained prior results offers an automatized approach to drip system scheduling with precision and effectiveness on crop irrigation. Irrigation scheduling offers an automated conservation of soil resources, water resources, human labour resources, and machine resources in agricultural cultivational farms. Scheduling in a drip system maximizes the irrigation efficiency more prior their collaborative efforts.

Authors Contribution

Okolotu Godspower Ikechukwu (Conceptualization; Methodology; Writing Original Draft; *etc*). Eje Brendan Eket (Visualization; Manuscript Review; *etc*). Akwenuke Onozogie Moses (Manuscript Review; *etc*). Okeke Chineze Glory (Manuscript Review; *etc*).

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***Okolotu G.I., Eje B.E., Akwenuke O.M., and Okeke C.G.**

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***Okolotu G.I., Eje B.E., Akwenuke O.M., and Okeke C.G.**